

VolEvol – D2 –

Criteria for the Objective Assessment of Quality and Diversity in Volume Visualization

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Index of Contents

Index of Contents.....	2
1 Introduction	3
2 Problem Formulation	4
3 Surface-based approaches	5
3.1 Gradient magnitude.....	6
3.2 Gradient orientation.....	7
3.3 Curvature magnitude.....	10
3.4 Visibility and occlusion.....	12
3.5 Color assignment.....	14
4 Image-based approaches.....	16
4.1 Case study	18
4.2 Methods from the state of the art	21
4.2.1 Methods based on traditional visual features.....	21
4.2.2 Methods based on deep visual features	23
4.2.3 Approaches based on end-to-end deep models.....	23
5 Conclusions.....	25
6 References	25

1 Introduction

Objective quality assessment in volume visualization is a crucial process aimed at quantifying the quality of rendered volumetric images or animations using measurable metrics and algorithms. This approach is essential to ensure that the visualizations accurately represent the underlying data and meet specific quality standards. The assessment of quality in computer graphics, visualization and image processing is a complex task, particularly due to the number of scenarios, use cases and problems encountered in the aforementioned fields, and also due to the subjective nature of quality. The objectives of VolEvol require a means of automatically measuring the quality of the visual information generated within the corresponding volume rendering pipeline. To this extent, we search for methods, algorithms and metrics that can be used by an optimizer to search for rendering parameters such that the resulting images adhere to our formulations on what constitutes quality. At the same time, similar metrics can be exploited such that the space of possible parameters can be more thoroughly explored, resulting in populations of images exhibiting diverse content.

This document presents our findings in terms of approaches that constitute good candidates for quality and diversity criteria, to be used as objectives and/or for defining feature spaces when automatically generating images from volume data. During the course of developing the VolEvol project, we realized that this is a problem of significant complexity, and it possibly constitutes the most elaborate aspect of the project. This is due to the sometimes vague nature of what constitutes a “quality” image, or what constitutes a “diverse” image set, and to the difficulty of incorporating such assessments into an automated search algorithm. In this context, our requirements for such metrics can be summarized as follows:

- Objective assessment: the methods should constitute means of objectively assessing quality and diversity in volume rendering. Though there is an inescapable subjective nature when it comes to quality assessment, such methods should come as close as possible to evaluating quality in a perceptually-relevant manner. Our reasoning for deciding such metrics can be surmised as “what would a user look for in the resulting image, that can be automatically measured?”.
- No-reference assessment: the most common quality assessment algorithms, particularly in image processing, use reference information or a ground truth against which to compare the resulting images. In VolEvol we are so far constrained to search for quality and diversity in a more-or-less “blind” manner – i.e. in absence of a reference or a concrete, already-available goal.

In our case, such metrics take the form of properties, descriptors and/or quality scores that can be determined from the volume data. We roughly divide such properties into two categories:

- Surface base features, that are derived from analysing the profiles of various surfaces identified from volume data sets.
- Image-based features, where image processing tools are used to analyse the images from the output of the volume rendering pipeline, resulting in quality scores with various interpretations.

In the rest of this document we present our findings in the aforementioned directions. Though the features identified thus far are good candidates for assessing quality and establishing diversity in volume rendered image, it is likely that the search for such features will extend for the duration of VolEvol, due to the complex nature of the quality assessment problem.

2 Problem Formulation

In VolEvol we aim to obtain images that represent relevant objects, features and structures from volume data. Such data can be thought of as a discretization of a region of space where each discrete position is associated with a numeric value that quantifies the physical properties of the medium at the corresponding spatial position. For the sake of consistency, we refer to these values as *densities*. Consequently, the volume data used in VolEvol is a regular grid of density values d from density domain D , such that each discrete position (x_i, y_i, z_i) from the data set has a corresponding value d_i . The distribution of the density values is an important criterion in identifying and representing objects of interest from within the data set. A very common scenario is that a structure of interest is identifiable using a specific density value, a density threshold, or a density range. Generating images from such data requires an exploration of the 3D space of the volume, during which important objects may be encountered, extracted, and given a visual representation. A crucial aspect of volume rendering is how the density values are handled during the traversal of the volume, how opacities and colors are assigned to the resulting samples, and how the resulting opacities and colors are combined to form a representation of the corresponding scene [1]. Considering the goals of VolEvol and the commonly-complex nature of volume data, during the course of development we adopted a more focused approach to identifying and representing meaningful information from the whole volume. Without loss of generalization, our reasoning is that meaningful, visually-relevant objects from volume data are bounded by sets of spatial positions with similar density values. This is a very common scenario for volume data resulting from acquisition devices such as 3D Computed Tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scanners. The objects of interest contained within the data are commonly bounded by a generally well-defined surface that exhibits consistent spatial coherence. In a 3D CT image, the scanned objects are delineated from the surrounding environment by an identifiable surface. In a meteorological scan, various atmospheric fronts and spatial patterns are also at well-established boundaries. A procedurally-generated volume usually relies on a generative approach that produces values from a well-defined domain and/or using a well-defined distribution. As such, we formulate the automated rendering problem to be solved by VolEvol as the task of identifying one or multiple relevant surfaces from the volume data. In this context, we define a surface as the set of positions within the volume data which share a common density, or which lie at the boundary determined by a density threshold. In the field of volume visualization, these sets of positions are known as *isosurfaces* – surfaces defined by similar density values. Each density value d from density domain D defines an isosurface. Of the total possible isosurfaces, there exists a subset which are representative of the important content of the volume data set, and as such are worth displaying. In our experience, the volume rendering problem becomes much less ambiguous if we treat the volume dataset as a family of isosurfaces, rather than as a continuous region of space with a certain distribution of data values. By handling the problem in this manner, we are

able to formulate much clearer criteria for selecting coherent, meaningful structures and surfaces to display from the volume, so that the resulting images are easily interpretable visually.

3 Surface-based approaches

During the course of the VolEvol project, our most successful attempts at clarifying the meaning of *objective quality* in volume data have relied on analyzing surfaces extracted from the volume data set. Our definition of a surface is one which is commonly used in the field of volume visualization: it is the set of positions within the volume data which share a common property. In our case, surface-based criteria are measurements which are based on analyzing the spatial properties and features of the isosurfaces contained within the volume data set. From our experience and studies within the field of volume visualization, we can claim without loss of generalization that visually-relevant isosurfaces lie at the boundaries of important objects that can be found in the volume dataset – an example would be the boundary between an object and its surrounding media. The primary criterion for making this separation are the density values from the volume data, which are representative of the physical properties of the various objects contained within. In a volume originating from a scanning device, different objects have different density values, making density a strong candidate for classifying the various structures found within the volume space [2].

In this context, we formulate the quality assessment problem as the task of finding meaningful isosurfaces from the volume data. We aim for isosurfaces and related quality assessment criteria that should meet certain standards, such as:

- The identified surfaces should be *coherent* – that is, the objects delineated by the surface should be easy to visually identify and interpret.
- The identified surfaces should be as less-fragmented as possible – that is, the surface should be a continuous area, unbroken into multiple pieces. In our experience, fragmentation is the common scenario for a majority of surfaces as defined by the density value domain, while only a minority of such surfaces are meaningful in that they represent useful, important structures and objects from the volume data.
- The features use no prior reference, that is, they are not weighed against a ground truth, since the formulation of the VolEvol tasks excludes reference images or “correct” reference values.
- The features used for assessing quality and establishing diversity should be relatively fast to compute. Since they are intended to be used as optimization criteria and are called many times during the iterations of the optimizer, they should be fast to calculate – several milliseconds at most. Therefore, we rely on criteria that are fast to determine, which excludes most approaches based on training a supervised model.

Our surface features are primarily based on determining a surface profile – that is, a map of values illustrating a geometric and/or spatial property of the portions of the surface that is visible to the viewer. A statistical analysis of such profiles allows the discrimination of meaningful isosurfaces against less usable ones. In the following sections, we exemplify several resulting surface features using a volume data set originating from a 3D CT medical scan.

3.1 Gradient magnitude

One of the most powerful criteria for choosing and characterizing a set of isosurfaces is using the derivatives of the volume data. In this manner, surfaces are chosen based on density variations within the volume data. The volume dataset can be defined as function $f : R^3 \rightarrow D$ which assigns density value d to position (x, y, z) from 3D space, the variation of density within the volume can be expressed via the gradient of function f (Eq. 1). We compute the gradient within the ray casting loop of our volume renderer using a central differences-based approach (Eq. 2), after having interpolated the volume data values via 3D texture filtering. The Δ parameter is used to control the extent of the finite differences used to approximate the gradient components. We generally choose the Δ values based on the resolution of the data set. We also account for the following important aspect: while there is a tendency to use small Δ values, since the smaller the Δ , the closer the approximated gradient is to the mathematically true one, larger Δ values are more robust to noise and antialiasing, which almost always cause numerical errors when working with such data, resulting in unwanted visual artefacts.

$$\bar{\nabla} f(x, y, z) = \left[\frac{\partial f}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\bar{\nabla} f(x, y, z) \approx \begin{bmatrix} \frac{f(x+\Delta, y, z) - f(x-\Delta, y, z)}{2\Delta} \\ \frac{f(x, y+\Delta, z) - f(x, y-\Delta, z)}{2\Delta} \\ \frac{f(x, y, z+\Delta) - f(x, y, z-\Delta)}{2\Delta} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Computing the gradient magnitude for an isosurface I_d , defined by density d , yields a set of values for the exposed sides of the surface which we refer to as the *gradient magnitude map*. Fig. 1 shows a few examples of isosurfaces, their corresponding gradient maps, and the distributions of gradient magnitudes for each isosurface. Analyzing the distribution of gradient magnitudes over the isosurface space yields powerful criteria for selecting important isosurfaces. The reasoning behind this interpretation is that isosurfaces depicting important objects lie at the boundaries of media with different densities. For example, in the case of a medical scan, different anatomical structures, tissues and items of interest are separable due to differences in their density values. This means that, statistically, important objects are defined by surfaces where there is significant difference between the densities on either side of the surface. Such surfaces are therefore identifiable as regions where gradient magnitudes are larger than elsewhere in the volume space. An effective way of measuring this property is to analyze the distributions of gradient magnitudes of visible surfaces and identify surfaces whose distributions are biased towards larger values. This concept is exemplified in Fig. 1. We consider the isosurfaces in Fig. 1(a),(b) to be of higher quality than those from Fig. 1(c),(d), since they depict more coherent and more easily identifiable structures. This is reflected in the distributions of gradient magnitudes in the bottom row of Fig. 1. For isosurfaces depicting more coherent structures and/or objects of interest, the distribution tends to be shifted toward the middle of the gradient magnitude domain, and the local maximum tends to be located in the

neighborhood of the median of the domain (Fig. 1(a),(b)). Conversely, lower quality isosurfaces, i.e. those depicting mixtures of partial objects and broken up, fragmented isosurfaces, tend to have their distributions shifted toward the lower part of the magnitude domain (Fig. 1(c),(d)). This property of the gradient magnitude allows us to choose important, diverse isosurfaces by forming optimization criteria based on the bias of the gradient distribution (for instance, the position of the global maximum within the magnitude domain). At the same time, diversity can be encouraged in the isosurface population by selecting isosurface candidates with distributions exhibiting different standard deviations from the global maximum.

Fig. 1. Examples of various isosurfaces (top row), their corresponding gradient magnitude maps (middle row) and resulting gradient magnitude distributions (bottom row).

3.2 Gradient orientation

Aside from the magnitude, another useful property of the gradient is its orientation. An effective manner of obtaining and studying the profile of a surface is to analyze the distribution and properties of the surface normals (i.e. vectors oriented perpendicular to the surface on any point on the surface). The directions of the normals yield important information on the geometric properties of the surface. For a perfectly flat surface, the normals have the same direction at any point. Surfaces exhibiting spatial variation (i.e. many “mountains” and “valleys”) tend to have a wide diversity of normal directions. At the same time, varied surface normal directions may indicate a noisy surface (i.e., a fragmented or rough surface that, while varied in geometric detail, does not outline meaningful structures). Generally, the normal direction is a powerful criterion for automatically determining the variation and the amount of detail shown by a

surface. A smoother, more coherent surface will have normals with a narrower range of directions (Fig. 2(a)), while for a more varied surface the normal vectors are more dispersed (Fig. 2(b)).

Fig. 2. Illustration of surface normals: (a) smoother / flatter surfaces tend to exhibit a narrower dispersion of normal directions; (b) surfaces with more spatial variation exhibit a greater dispersion of normal directions.

In volume space, an important surface is a set of points which typically lie at the boundary between media with different physical properties, which translates to different density values. Consequently, for such surfaces, the gradient vectors are oriented towards the most significant density variation, which is in a direction roughly perpendicular to the surface. For isosurfaces, gradient vectors are analogous to the surface normals in polygonal-based surfaces from traditional computer graphics. Therefore, we can characterize an isosurface in terms of its exposed level of detail by studying the orientations of the gradient vectors of the positions on the isosurface. This provides us with another powerful criterion for assessing the quality of an isosurface and choosing meaningful isosurfaces from the volume space. For any point in volume space, we determine the orientation of the gradient vector at that point by assessing the angle between the gradient vector and the vector representing the viewing direction at that point. Let G be the gradient vector determined at a random point (x, y, z) in volume space, and V the viewing vector, i.e. the vector representing the direction of the viewer looking at point (x, y, z) . The direction of G is normal to the isosurface passing through (x, y, z) , corresponding to density d at position (x, y, z) . We determine the orientation $\omega(G)$ of gradient vector G by assessing the angle between G and V . We achieve this computationally using the cosine similarity between the two vectors (Eq. 3). Higher values of $\omega(G)$ mean that G forms a larger angle with viewing vector V .

$$\omega(\vec{G}) = 1 - \frac{\vec{G} \cdot \vec{V}}{\|\vec{G}\| \|\vec{V}\|} \quad (3)$$

Using this metric, we can easily construct a profile of any isosurface from the orientations determined at the positions in volume space through which it passes. The total orientations of the exposed sides of the surface form the *gradient orientation map*. From this map we can derive criteria for assessing the quality of any particular isosurface, as well as for selecting the most useful ones. In this context, our reasoning is as follows:

- Surfaces with sparse gradient orientations tend to be smoother, flatter and featureless – i.e. such a surface is poor in geometric details (“mountains”, “valleys”, etc.). At the same time,

such surfaces also tend to be more continuous and coherent, i.e., less fragmented and easier to interpret visually.

- Surfaces with a wider range of gradient orientations tend to exhibit a larger amount of geometric details, i.e. the surface shown more spatial features of the object it outlines. At the same time, more gradient orientations are also characteristic of fragmented, incoherent and/or discontinuous surfaces, which when displayed tend to exhibit visual noise.

Fig. 3. Examples of various isosurfaces (top row), their gradient orientation maps (middle row) and corresponding distributions (bottom row).

Considering the reasoning above, we can formulate a criterion for assessing isosurface quality by analyzing the distribution of gradient orientations. Several examples of isosurfaces and their corresponding maps and gradient orientation distributions are provided in Fig. 3. A fast, effective way of interpreting the distributions is via their uniformity. Cleaner, coherent isosurfaces tend to have distributions which are less uniform. This is visible in Fig. 3(a)(b) where higher quality, more coherent isosurfaces have unbalanced distributions that tend to favor lower gradient angles. The less features and “cleaner” the isosurface, the less equalized and less uniform the distribution. Conversely, as the isosurfaces become richer in features, but also noisier and more fragmented, so to the distributions tend to flatten, i.e. they become closer to uniform. This property of the isosurface profile is easily measurable and constitutes a reliable criterion for selecting isosurfaces conforming to an objective interpretation of quality. At the same time, diverse isosurfaces can be chosen based on the same criterion of uniformity. Various

isosurfaces exhibiting varied amounts of details can therefore be incorporated into the resulting images.

3.3 Curvature magnitude

The curvature of a surface refers to how the shape of the surface deviates from being perfectly flat. It is a fundamental concept in geometry and mathematics and plays a significant role in various fields such as physics, engineering, and computer graphics. Local curvature describes how a small section of a surface is curved or bent at a specific point. Curvature allows us to distinguish between flat surfaces and curved surfaces. A flat surface has zero curvature, which means it is locally indistinguishable from a plane. In contrast, curved surfaces have non-zero curvature, and the curvature provides information about the extent and nature of the curvature. Curvature provides information about the local behavior of a surface. By calculating the curvature at a specific point on the surface, you can determine whether that point is part of a flat region or a region with some degree of curvature. This information is essential for understanding the surface's shape. Curvature is instrumental in defining surface features, such as ridges, valleys, and creases. High curvature regions often correspond to sharp features, while low curvature regions correspond to flatter or smoother portions of the surface. The magnitude of curvature quantifies the amount of bending or curvature at a particular point on the surface. This information helps in characterizing how the surface deviates from being flat. High curvature values indicate strong bending, while low values suggest a flatter region.

There are various mathematical and numeric means of determining the curvature of the surface. Most such methods rely on computing the second derivative in 3D space at the surface points, based on which multiple relevant directions and measurements may be determined, such as principal curvatures. Most such methods tend to be computationally-intensive and not suitable for real-time applications. We opt for an approximation of curvature magnitude, which is relatively fast and easy to compute, and allows us to derive reliable surface profiles. We aim to characterize isosurfaces based on the level at which they feature curved portions illustrating important spatial details. At the same time, high degrees of curvature magnitudes may indicate a surface that is overloaded with spatial features and is therefore difficult to interpret visually.

Our measurement of curvature magnitude is based on estimating the Hessian matrix at each point on the exposed sides of the isosurface. Let $f(x, y, z)$ be the function describing the volume space at any point x, y, z , as mentioned in Section 3.1. The curvature magnitude K can be expressed using the Hessian $H(f)$ and the gradient ∇f at each corresponding point on the isosurface, as shown in Eq. 4. As in previous Sections, we plot the curvature map of the isosurface and the corresponding distribution of curvature magnitudes (Fig. 4).

$$K = - \frac{\begin{vmatrix} \mathbf{H}(f) & \nabla f^T \\ \nabla f & 0 \end{vmatrix}}{|\nabla f|^4} = - \frac{\begin{vmatrix} \partial^2 f / \partial x^2 & \partial^2 f / \partial x \partial y & \partial^2 f / \partial x \partial z & \partial f / \partial x \\ \partial^2 f / \partial x \partial y & \partial^2 f / \partial y^2 & \partial^2 f / \partial y \partial z & \partial f / \partial y \\ \partial^2 f / \partial x \partial z & \partial^2 f / \partial y \partial z & \partial^2 f / \partial z^2 & \partial f / \partial z \\ \partial f / \partial x & \partial f / \partial y & \partial f / \partial z & 0 \end{vmatrix}}{|\nabla f|^4} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 4. Examples of various isosurfaces (top row), their curvature magnitude maps (middle row) and corresponding distributions (bottom row).

We interpret the distributions of curvature magnitudes according to their prominence at both ends of the curvature domain. Isosurfaces depicting clean, coherent surfaces with only a few, but important details, such as the surfaces in Fig. 4 (a), (b) which illustrate facial features, have distributions which are heavily biased toward the lower end of the curvature domain. For surfaces which are relatively featureless, save for a few important geometric details, the distribution of curvature magnitudes is prominent in the subdomain of low curvature values, save for a small peak at the opposite end of the domain. In the opposite case, surfaces which show a rich set of various geometric shapes have a multitude of high-curvature regions. As seen in Fig. 4(c), (d), surfaces with complex, diverse spatial features, or less coherent surfaces formed from multiple fragments, exhibit distributions which are heavily biased towards the higher-value end of the curvature domain. An assessment of the shape of the distribution allows us to formulate optimization objectives using various types of reasoning when it comes to defining objective quality: a high quality surface may be one which is relatively flat and continuous, save

for a few important geometric details – a property which is quantifiable via a proper assessment of the distribution of curvature magnitudes. Another formulation of quality in this respect may be in favor of surfaces which are richly-detailed, but which, at the same time, are coherent enough to be visually interpretable. Irregular or sudden changes in curvature can indicate surface roughness or discontinuities. Curvature analysis helps determine how smoothly a surface transitions from one point to another, and it plays a crucial role in formulating adequate features for the measurement of objective quality.

3.4 Visibility and occlusion

Visibility and occlusion are pivotal aspects of volume visualization, influencing the effectiveness of conveying insights from volumetric data. Achieving optimal visibility while managing occlusion challenges requires a careful balance of rendering techniques, transfer functions, and interaction methods to provide viewers with clear, informative, and comprehensible visualizations of complex three-dimensional datasets. Occlusion, on the other hand, is the concept of objects or structures in the volumetric data obstructing the view of other objects behind them. Occlusion is a natural phenomenon that occurs in three-dimensional space, and it plays a critical role in volume visualization because it can obscure important details within the dataset. To address occlusion, visualization techniques often employ methods like transparency and depth sorting. Transparency allows the viewer to see through partially opaque structures, revealing obscured information. Depth sorting ensures that objects closer to the viewer are rendered in front of objects farther away, minimizing unwanted occlusion effects.

For our purposes, we primarily use occlusion information to ensure proper focus and context when multiple isosurfaces are displayed. In such a scenario, the opacities of various rendered isosurfaces may be adjusted such that occluded objects, or objects contained within other objects, are made visible, while other neighboring occluding structures are maintained in view. A high quality image may display multiple objects and structures without causing visual overload. Similarly, a diverse set of images would show multiple combinations of objects with opacities adjusted such that different details are visible to different degrees in the resulting images. The procedural determination of visibility and occlusion play an essential role in such situations.

Fig. 5. Evaluation of the level of occlusion of a sample point s , based on sample points s_i in between s and the viewer.

There are multiple means of computing occlusion, most of which require either a preprocessing step or expensive real-time computations. We use a computationally-cheap and fast method of approximating occlusion, making this determination easy to incorporate into our rendering pipeline. Essentially, the level of occlusion of a point in a volume data set refers to the degree to which the isosurface passing through the point is covered by other structures inbetween it and the viewer. There are two components that play a defining role in assessing visibility, considering the level of occlusion: the targeted isosurface's own opacity, and the accumulated opacities of other isosurfaces in front of it, or enclosing it.

The concept behind evaluating occlusion is presented in Fig. 5. Given any point s with opacity α_s , the level of occlusion Ω_s is determined using opacities α_i of points s_i on isosurfaces located inbetween s and the viewer position (Eq. 5).

$$\Omega_s = \alpha_s e^{-\sum \alpha_i} \quad (5)$$

The resulting levels of occlusion are exemplified in Fig. 6. The main image from Fig. 6(a) is a representation of multiple isosurfaces with different colors and opacity levels. Fig. 6(b) shows the estimated levels of occlusion of each individual isosurface. A successful rendering of volume data would display multiple such structures in an image that is easy to analyze visually, where most objects of interest are clearly visible. Particularly in the case of medical imaging, many anatomical structures are mixed together and difficult to visually separate, requiring a careful search through the occlusion space to determine a proper opacity transfer function which results in a quality image.

Fig. 6. Illustration of visibility, determined using the level of occlusion: (a) a complex rendering showing multiple isosurfaces; (b) the levels of visibility of each individual isosurface, represented as intensities in visibility maps.

As a classification criterion and as a feature used to assess and obtain quality images, the level of occlusion has multiple applications in volume rendering. There are many scenarios where an object or structure of interest is hidden within other surfaces, to the point where conventional classification methods cannot isolate it without almost completely removing other important structures in front of it. In such situations, the correct evaluation of occlusion is a crucial aspect in revealing the object of focus, while maintaining the context provided by neighboring objects. We illustrate this principle in Fig. 7. In the image from Fig. 7(a), where conventional density and gradient-based classification was employed, it is difficult to isolate certain hidden objects (in this case, brain vasculature) without completely removing tissue types. Occluding structures cannot be preserved without simultaneously bringing the objects of interest into view. When incorporating occlusion-based features into the rendering pipeline, it becomes possible to reveal previously hidden objects while at the same time showing other structures containing potentially-useful context-related visual information (Fig. 7(b)).

Fig. 7. Two renderings of the same dataset: (a) Traditional rendering methods cannot be used to highlight hidden structures such as cerebral vasculature; (b) By incorporating occlusion-based features into the rendering pipeline, hidden structures can be revealed while maintaining neighboring structures into view.

3.5 Color assignment

The formulation of the volume visualization problem as an isosurface identification and rendering task makes it much simpler to assign colors to the resulting surfaces. The color assignment task is reduced to deciding on a color for each individual isosurface. The search space within the VolEvol environment is narrowed to key points defined by three key elements: density D , opacity A , and color C . In our context, we do not need the precision of a three dimensional color space such as RGB to select colors from. It is enough that we establish the color of each isosurface from a predefined color table (as is the case, for instance, with images using a color index format). The color assignment task is trivial when rendering a single isosurface. In scenarios where multiple semi-transparent isosurfaces are simultaneously depicted, a quality image contains a combination of colors that adhere to the following fundamental criteria:

- The chosen color scheme should make it easy to visually identify individual isosurfaces – in other words, the distribution of color should maximize the visibilities of the depicted structures.
- The color combination should not result in a visual overload of the image or in an image which is difficult to visually perceive due to “striking” color combinations.

Consequently, color assignment is an aesthetic choice to a much greater extent than in the scenarios presented in previous sections. When establishing color combinations, we consider the following important aspects when formulating an optimization objective:

- Mood and message: Different colors evoke different emotions and themes. For instance, warm colors like reds and oranges can create a sense of energy, while cooler colors like blues and greens can convey calmness.

- Limited color palette: in order to avoid a chaotic appearance, the color palette is limited to a few key hues. Two or three dominant colors can work well together, creating cohesion while minimizing visual clutter. Additional neutral or complementary colors are added as needed, to be used as accents or highlights.

- Color contrast: High-contrast combinations, such as black and white, or complementary colors like red and green, can make objects stand out distinctly. However, they can also be visually striking. Low-contrast combinations, such as different shades of the same color, can create a more subtle and harmonious look.

- Depth using color: To distinguish overlapping objects, variations in color intensity, saturation, or brightness may be employed. Objects in the foreground can have more vibrant or saturated colors, while those in the background can be desaturated or lighter in hue. This technique helps create a sense of depth and dimension in the scene.

Balanced warm and cool tones: Combining warm and cool colors can create a visually pleasing contrast without being too striking. For example, pairing warm yellows or oranges with cool blues or purples can balance the scene and make each object distinct.

Our main strategy for color selection is to choose the color distribution in the 3D scene based on the opacities of the rendered isosurfaces and the level of occlusion of each isosurface. While there are multiple considerations in this regard considering chromatics, user perception, color contrast and aesthetics, our strategy for choosing choice of a suitable color combination can be distilled as follows:

- When a single opaque isosurface is rendered, nearly any color will suffice, as long as it is distinct enough from the background. We primarily make this distinction based on hue (Fig. 8 (a))

- When multiple isosurfaces are displayed with different opacities, such that multiple ones are visible past a visibility threshold, the colors of the respective isosurfaces is such that the color hues are spread far apart from each other. This generally ensures a good color contrast and good visibility for each individual isosurface. Since in VolEvol we do not target volume data from a specific field, we do not choose color based on the type of material (i.e. based on the type of tissue for medical scans). Rather, we aim for a color combination that prioritizes perception and

the visual distinction of each isosurface even though certain color combination may result in a non-photorealistic scene (Fig. 8 (b), (c)).

Fig. 8. Multiple renderings of the same dataset showing different isosurfaces with various opacities. (a) when a single opaque isosurface is displayed, a single color which is visible against the background suffices; (b)(c) when multiple isosurfaces are displayed using various opacities, contrasting color combinations are selected so that the underlying structures are visible without causing a visual overload of the resulting image.

4 Image-based approaches

Quality assessment methods which we label as “image-based” make use of image processing and analysis techniques to evaluate the quality of the output of the volume renderer, in 2D image-space. Thus, such methods are applied at the end of the volume rendering pipeline and are used to assess the quality of the images produced by the rendering process.

Image processing and analysis techniques have become increasingly essential in the field of image quality assessment, particularly in the context of no-reference quality assessment (NRQA). NRQA refers to the evaluation of image quality without a reference image for comparison, making it a crucial tool in various domains like multimedia, medical imaging, and remote sensing. In the context of VolEvol, given the absence of reference images to assess quality against, we explore the role of image processing and analysis techniques in NRQA. Thus, one of the primary challenges in NRQA is the absence of a pristine reference image to gauge the quality of the test image. To address this, image processing methods are employed to extract relevant features and information from the image. These features can range from simple statistical measures like image contrast and brightness to more complex attributes such as texture, sharpness, and color distribution. Techniques like histogram analysis, wavelet

transforms, and gradient-based algorithms are used to quantify these features, providing valuable insights into the image's quality.

Once these features are extracted, image analysis techniques are applied to interpret the data and derive quality scores. Machine learning algorithms, including support vector machines, deep neural networks, and decision trees, are frequently employed to establish models that relate the extracted features to perceived image quality. These models can then predict the quality of images without relying on a reference image. Additionally, techniques such as image segmentation and region-of-interest analysis enable NRQA systems to focus on specific areas of interest within an image, providing more granular quality assessments.

Moreover, image processing and analysis techniques in NRQA often incorporate human perception models, aligning the assessments with how humans perceive image quality. Psychophysical studies and perceptual models help researchers understand the subjective nature of image quality and guide the development of NRQA algorithms that mimic human judgment. These models consider factors like visual acuity, contrast sensitivity, and spatial frequency characteristics to make quality predictions that align closely with human assessments.

Several aspects are important considering the role of such techniques:

- **Feature Extraction:** Image processing techniques are pivotal in NRQA as they facilitate the extraction of informative features from the images. These features encompass a wide spectrum of characteristics, including structural, statistical, and perceptual attributes. Structural features may encompass edge sharpness, contour information, and local details. Statistical features involve measures of contrast, brightness, and color distribution. Perceptual features could include texture complexity, visual saliency, and global/local sharpness. These extracted features serve as the foundation for subsequent quality assessment.
- **Machine Learning:** Image analysis techniques often involve machine learning algorithms. By utilizing a dataset of images with associated quality scores, machine learning models can be trained to establish the relationship between extracted features and perceived image quality. Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and Random Forests are some of the common algorithms employed in NRQA. These models learn to predict image quality, allowing for the automatic assessment of images without the need for human reference ratings.
- **Multi-Feature Fusion:** To enhance the accuracy of NRQA systems, image processing techniques can be used to combine multiple features from different domains. For instance, combining statistical features (e.g., contrast and color) with perceptual features (e.g., texture) often results in more robust quality assessment. Fusion methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or simple linear combinations can be applied to combine these features effectively.
- **Human Perception Modeling:** Image processing and analysis in NRQA can be further refined by incorporating models of human perception. These models are designed to mimic how humans perceive image quality. They consider aspects such as the Human Visual System (HVS) characteristics, including contrast sensitivity, visual acuity, and the effects of visual

masking. Integrating human perception models into NRQA algorithms makes them more aligned with human judgment, leading to more accurate quality predictions.

- Application Diversity: NRQA techniques are not limited to a specific domain. They find applications in various fields like multimedia content delivery, medical imaging, satellite imagery, and even security and surveillance. In the medical field, for example, NRQA can be used to evaluate the quality of medical images such as X-rays, MRIs, and CT scans, ensuring that accurate diagnoses are made.

While there exists multiple directions and techniques with regard to NRQA, for the purposes of VolEvol image-space techniques have so far proven less usable than surface and volume-space approaches. While, as of the writing of this report, we are continuously experimenting with various solutions in terms of assessing quality and encouraging diversity, several key aspects are worth noting:

- For the objectives of VolEvol we require quality assessment methods that are reasonable fast. Considering that much methods are used to form objectives for evolutionary optimizers, we are very much constrained by the processing times of such methods and can only rely on the fastest ones.
- Many state-of-the-art quality assessment methods rely on supervised neural network-based models. In our experience, even pre-trained models take a very long time to execute (at least several dozen seconds per image, even for images as small as 512x512). Consequently, at this stage of the VolEvol development we do not rely on such models, given the lengthy runtimes of an optimizer which makes use of such a method as its objective.
- Image-space methods generally address the notion of “quality” differently from the language of VolEvol. We seek methods which assess image quality in terms of the perception and visual interpretation of the objects represented within the images. Conversely, most image-space methods handle the concept of quality in terms of the visual fidelity of the image. Such methods assess the input image with regard to: distortions, compression artifacts, pixelation, noise, blurring, aliasing etc. Since the VolEvol renderer does not generate images which suffer from acquisition or compression-related problems, we have to selectively employ image-space techniques so as to adapt to our own requirements for quality assessment.

4.1 Case study

Image-space quality assessment methods employ various forms of processing and analysis steps on the output image and output a quality score, representing the quantified assessment of the deduced level of image quality. We exemplify the use of such an approach using one of the most popular NRQA methods, the blind/referenceless image spatial quality evaluator (BRISQUE) [3]. As a no-reference approach, BRISQUE is designed to objectively and automatically assess the perceptual quality of digital images without the need for reference images. This referenceless quality assessment is particularly valuable in applications where a pristine reference image is unavailable, as is currently the case of VolEvol. BRISQUE operates on the principle that natural images exhibit certain statistical regularities, and deviations from these regularities can indicate image quality issues. It quantifies image quality by analyzing various statistical features

extracted from the image, including contrast, brightness, and spatial frequency characteristics. These features are then used to train a machine learning model, typically a Support Vector Machine (SVM), to predict the quality score of an image. One of the key strengths of BRISQUE is its ability to provide reliable quality assessments for a wide range of image distortions and artefacts, such as compression artefacts, noise, blurring, and more. It has found applications in various domains, including image and video compression, image enhancement, and quality control in the media and entertainment industry. Additionally, BRISQUE has been used in combination with other image processing techniques to optimize and enhance image quality automatically, making it a valuable tool in many image-related applications where image quality is critical.

Fig 9. Images illustrating isosurfaces of various densities, and their corresponding BRISQUE scores (lower values are better)

We have found that methods such as BRISQUE can reliably assess quality in volume rendering images which primarily suffer from partial pixelation. This means that such methods can discriminate images where the represented isosurfaces are heavily fragmented such that their projection in image space results in a noisy, pixelated representation. Thus, such image space methods favor renderings where the resulting images are cleaner, smoother and present fewer regions with “rogue” pixels which appear as low quality noise or distortions. We exemplify this concept in Fig. 9, where various isosurfaces are depicted, along with the corresponding scores resulting from applying BRISQUE on the resulting images. Lower scores correspond to images

with a “cleaner” aspect, presenting less pixel noise and regions that may be interpreted as distortions or graphical artefacts. We generally find that better scores are obtained for images depicting less pixelation or fragmentation of the visible structures. This is particularly valid for isosurfaces found in regions “inbetween” meaningful objects and structures for the volume dataset. Isosurfaces corresponding to boundaries of meaningful objects are generally better defined and result in cleaner images which are easier to perceive visually, while other isosurfaces found in intermediate regions result in less coherent images exhibiting what image-space NRQA methods interpret as noise or visible distortions.

A more complete depiction of the usefulness of such methods is illustrated in Fig. 10, where we represent the BRISQUE scores of images generated from isosurfaces over the entire density domain. Regions of the graph with lower scores correspond to density subdomains where more visually relevant isosurfaces are found. For instance, such regions may be found in the neighborhood of the global minimum of the quality score, where the displayed isosurfaces tend to correspond to images of higher visual quality. As previously stated, images which are considered of higher quality by methods such as BRISQUE tend to illustrate more coherent isosurfaces which generally correspond to more relevant objects from the volume data set.

An important downside of image-space methods is that, unlike the surface-based approaches from previous sections, they do not analyze the shape and spatial properties of the underlying objects from the volume data set. Rather, such methods only see the projected version of such structures, in the 2D space of the output image. Consequently, such methods do not analyze the volume data set in depth, but rather only the resulting rendering.

Fig. 10. Graph illustrating BRISQUE scores over the entire density range of the volume data set (lower values are better).

An additional disadvantage of such methods is that they generally assess image quality in terms of noise, pixelation and distortions, as opposed to volume-space approaches which also account for the quality of the surfaces of partially or entirely visible structures. Thus, such methods can only be used to assess quality if the rendering process generates images where the 2D

projections of the displayed structures may be interpreted as being noisy, pixelated or distorted. As seen in Fig. 9, BRISQUE does not easily differentiate between isosurfaces whose corresponding images are relatively “clean” of apparent noise or pixelation.

Throughout the development of VolEvol we will be continuously experimenting with such approaches in order to perfect our understanding of their usefulness and benefits in terms of assessing quality and ensuring diversity in the rendered image set. Furthermore, the issue of objective quality assessment in image processing and visualization is far from being definitively answered in the related fields of research.

4.2 Methods from the state of the art

The field of image processing and analysis is extremely broad and many methods have been proposed within the related state of the art in terms of solving the problem of objective quality assessment of 2D images. As such, in support of our efforts to find a solution suitable to our objectives, we present a brief survey of relevant work from the related fields of research.

Most Non-reference Image Quality Assessment (NR-IQA) approaches refer to 2D images. Recent research could be divided into two main directions:

- Extract traditional or deep visual features and evaluate their deviations from statistical regularities (which are expected in high-quality images), directly or through a regressor.
- Design an end-to-end (deep) model which integrates feature extraction and NR-IQA.

The key aspect of these approaches is finding relevant features which can illustrate the irregularities specific to distorted images. When the number of features is reduced, the distortions can be directly evaluated by analysing the deviations between the distribution of features in normal and distorted images. Typically, Generalised Gaussian models are adopted. Another option is to describe the feature distribution using statistical metrics like mean, skewness, variance, etc., and train a regressor to evaluate image quality based on this compact representation. Methods based on traditional features are usually faster than those using deep features. They thus allow an effective integration into genetic optimisation approaches. However, deep features result through a better understanding of image layouts and can better illustrate local distortions.

4.2.1 Methods based on traditional visual features

The BRISQUE method [3] mentioned in the previous section is one of the most popular indicators for NR-IQA. As mentioned before, this method exploits the fact that natural images have certain regular statistical properties. The visual attributes used for analysis are the locally normalized luminance, and the products of locally normalized luminance values computed for pairs of neighbors along four directions: horizontal, vertical, main-diagonal, and secondary-diagonal. All these variables are expected to fit a Generalized Gaussian distribution for the normal/ high-quality images. The coefficients describing the shape and the variance of feature distributions are set as inputs for a support vector regressor which provides the BRISQUE score. The dataset used for training includes both normal and distorted images.

In extension to BRISQUE, Natural Image Quality Assessment (NIQE) [4] uses only normal samples to build a natural scene statistical model. This expands the usability of the model to any type of image distortion. The features extracted from undistorted images are fit to a multivariate Gaussian distribution and the distortions of the testing images are evaluated based on the deviation from these „natural“ distributions (Eq. 6):

$$D = \sqrt{(v_1 - v_2)^T \frac{(C_1 + C_2)^{-1}}{2} (v_1 - v_2)} \quad (6)$$

where v_1, v_2 are the mean vectors and C_1, C_2 are the covariance matrices corresponding to the multivariate Gaussian models of natural and distorted images, respectively. The features result only from patches with high sharpness, after local normalization. NIQE has been successfully used for different types of data, from medical images [5] to landscapes.

An improvement for NIQE is presented in [6]. Here, a set of filters is generated using Independent Component Analysis (ICA) applied to the patches extracted from undistorted images. This reduces the impact of redundancy specific to natural scenes, to improve the relevance of features. For undistorted images, the histogram of each component is also expected to fit a Generalised Gaussian Distribution (GGD). The NR-IQA score results by exploiting the Kullback–Leibler divergence (KLD) between the feature distribution specific to distorted images and a GGD.

[7] introduces the Visual Parameter Measurement Index (VPMI) for non-reference IQA. VPMI results as the product between the average entropy computed for the R, G, and B channels, the average luminance, the logarithm of the average gradient, and the average chroma factor. The last term relies on the histogram of intensities. High values of VPMI are expected for high-quality images.

Some indicators are defined for particular types of images. For instance, [8] proposes metrics specific to CT scans, like the bone contrast to noise ratio, which relies on the difference between CT numbers related to bones and subcutaneous fat, or trabecular sharpness defined as the ratio of voxels in a volume of interest that are not intermediate CT numbers. A high trabecular sharpness results in high-quality images, where the trabecular structure is well separated from the bone marrow. [9] uses contrast-to-noise and signal-to-noise ratios for MRI images and shows that these features have a large variability, relying on acquisition devices, which might disturb IQA.

[10] and [11] consider features like wavelet/DCT coefficients and singular values. Symmetric KLD is used to evaluate the deviation of the first-digit distribution from the distribution established by Benford’s law. The resulting deviations are passed to regression models trained to compute the NR-IQA scores.

[12] produces an enhanced image by histogram equalization. Then, the NR-IQA score is computed by a support vector regressor, using some features which describe the similitude between the original and enhanced images, like SSIM, histogram-based entropy, and cross-entropy. For high-quality images, reduced variations between the original and enhanced images are expected.

[13] uses attributes like the mutual information between the entropy on R, G, and B channels, the mean and skewness of the entropy computed on patches, and the mutual information between Gabor-filtered images (defined for 2 frequencies x 4 orientations). These attributes are also passed to an SVM to compute the NR-IQA scores.

[14] extracts feature maps with bi-Laplacian filters, high-boost filters (enhancing high frequencies), and high-order derivative filters applied in the YCbCr space. Then the mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis values computed in the neighborhoods of relevant key points are passed to a regressor.

[15] uses a one-sample t-test for pooling multiple pixel-wise features, instead of simple statistics like mean. This technique permits to highlight small, distorted regions which are less visible via average pooling.

4.2.2 Methods based on deep visual features

Deep features are usually extracted by means convolutional neural networks (CNN) that were pre-trained for image classification. [16] uses images resized for different scaling factors and extracts semantic deep features with ResNet50. The approach aggregates local, medium and global features, to analyse image quality. The mean and the standard deviations of these features are passed to partial least square regressor for computing the quality scores. The results show that the aggregation of features from different layers of ResNet50 is useful for IQA.

In [17], the features are extracted from patches, using also ResNet50. The paper highlights the advantages of using features maps from different layers of the deep feature extractor; however, the deepest features seem to be the most helpful for this task. The quality scores are computed via partial least square regression using refined statistics, which includes mean and standard deviation, quantiles, moments etc.

[18] suggests a CNN with dropout layers for feature extraction. The image is forwarded multiple times through this CNN, to use different neural architectures due to the dropout option. High-quality images produce latent encodings of reduced variation, hence the mean distance between resulting encodings is used for IQA scores. Although the results are promising, the procedure is time consuming, as the authors recommend about 100 evaluations per image.

A solution for MRI quality assessment is presented in [19]. Features are extracted with ResNet18 and ResNet50 and the fusion is done after dimensionality reduction performed with Principal Component Analysis.

4.2.3 Approaches based on end-to-end deep models

The recent success of deep models has encouraged their widespread use for IQA. End-to-end learning supports a proper configuration of the feature extractor, in line with the particularities of IQA, therefore, many CNN-based models are ranked with top performances on <https://paperswithcode.com/task/no-reference-image-quality-assessment>. However, these approaches request large training datasets and large execution times for inference.

In [20], the features are extracted by Inception-ResNet-v2 and an encoder – decoder architecture with an MLP head is used for calculating the IQA scores. This paper also presents a method based on student-teacher architecture for semi-supervised learning.

Because human- annotated images are difficult to obtain, [21] uses a CNN-based Siamese architecture, to rank pairs of images according to their quality. Then, a branch from the Siamese architecture is additionally tuned for IQA data.

[22] considers multi-scale features extracted by convolutional layers and an attention mechanism for fusing the resulting maps. The head obtains the normalised distribution of quality scores.

The model proposed in [23] exploits feature maps extracted through convolutional layers, a texture maps and a saliency map indicating the foreground regions. The head devoted to quality score computation is formed of fully connected layers.

[24] uses a CNN trained w. r. t. a contrastive objective function to evaluate IQ – CONTRIQUE. The loss function considers the similarity between pairs of images belonging to the same class (normal or distorted).

In [25], the model internally constructs the pristine image, starting from available feature maps. The resulting image is used as an extra reference during training. The fusion of features extracted from image patches is done with gated recurrent units. [26] proposes a model for evaluating the performance of super-resolution algorithms. QMRNet uses the encoder from ResNet18, and a head formed of fully connected layers.

[27] refers to artificial images, which usually do not hold the same statistical regularities as natural images. In this context, the deep model extracts multi-scale features from patches and analyses the deviations obtained between the feature distributions of pristine and distorted images, to compute appropriate quality scores.

[28] uses a transformer with encoder – decoder structure, which is firstly trained to produce the error map for a disturbed image. Then, the error maps are fused with the features maps provided by another transformer. The head used for regression includes fully connected layers.

The model introduced in [29] includes two main branches. A branch extracts features and offers a preliminary processing with two fully connected layers. The second branch implements a multiscale attention mechanism. All resulting features are passed to a multi-layer perceptron block, for regression.

5 Conclusions

We consider that the methods presented in this report constitute a reliable basic for assessing quality and encouraging diversity in images obtained from a volume renderer. So far, surface-based methods have proven to be the most reliable means of assessing the representations of volume data, while image-based feature extraction methods offer alternative metrics which complement the aforementioned volume-space techniques with means of analyzing output images in a post-rendering step. At the same time, we realized that this aspect of VolEvol is easily the most challenging, and searching for suitable criteria for measuring objective quality will likely extend for the duration of the project. As mentioned in previous sections, this problem is still not fully answered in the related state of the art. As we improve our understanding of this field and gain increased experience with using the presented methods to form optimization criteria for evolutionary algorithms, we strive to further clarify the meaning of quality and diversity in volume visualization and to provide automated means of obtaining sets of quality and diverse representation of volume data sets.

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